

Towards FAIR Research Data Management

Comparing and Aligning Container Concepts and Technologies

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Abstract

The management of research data is undergoing a critical transformation, driven by the increasing importance of the FAIR principles [1] (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable). As research data grows in volume, complexity, and diversity, new technologies are emerging to ensure its long-term storage, accessibility, and usability. Among these, container-based approaches for Research Data Management (RDM) have gained significant traction across disciplines. An essential aspect is the various software based solutions which are to be put into the container as well, since data without software becomes useless very soon. However, a fragmented landscape of concepts and implementations risks hampering the broader objectives of interoperability, reusability, and reproducibility. An important aspect is also the long-term storage and accessibility, interoperability i.e. the means to enact with the data and software after long time periods. E.g. the current requirement of the DFG to make research data available is 10 years.

This workshop aims to bring together researchers, infrastructure providers, developers, and data stewards to discuss, compare, and align container concepts and technologies that support FAIR RDM practices. We seek to explore a variety of solutions, from domain-specific efforts like RO-Crate[2] (Research Object Crate) in digital humanities and life sciences, to more general-purpose approaches such as BagIt[3] containers for digital preservation, BDBag[4] or Data Lad ([5]for big data packaging, and emerging containerization strategies around data lakes and computational reproducibility platforms (e.g., Docker[6] and Singularity[7] integrated workflows). Comprehensive approaches would be work of the Galaxy project[8] or the RDMC [9] currently being developed in NFDIxCS.

Major challenges are

- What constitutes a “Research Data Management Container” in different disciplines?
- How do current container concepts address metadata capture, versioning, access control, and long-term preservation?

- Which standards and protocols can bridge disciplinary gaps to support interoperability across research domains and may be even across technologies?
- How can container technologies be embedded into daily research workflows without adding undue burden on researchers?

A particular focus will be given to the interplay between technical solutions and policy requirements, such as persistent identifiers, provenance tracking, and compliance with data protection regulations (e.g., GDPR). We will also highlight successful cross-disciplinary initiatives, for example, the adoption of the concepts of FAIR Data Objects[10] and RO-Crate metadata schemata by environmental science projects, the use of BagIt-based archives in biomedical research or use the comprehensive concepts like the RDMC.

Participants will engage in breakout sessions to map the requirements and solutions specific to their fields and identify shared challenges and opportunities for collaboration. The goal is to foster a networked community that can drive the standardization, development, and adoption of interoperable container solutions for FAIR data management.

We call upon researchers, developers, infrastructure providers, and funding agencies to join forces in this effort. By sharing experiences, aligning technologies, and identifying converging standards, we can collectively build a sustainable ecosystem for research data containers that fulfill the FAIR principles not just at the time of data publication, but throughout the entire data lifecycle.

Join us in shaping the future of FAIR research data management!

Resources

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